

Supplementary material for

Enhancing the Learning of Database Access Programming using Continuous Integration and Aspect Oriented Programming

In this document, we explain the steps to install the **AspectJ Development Tools (AJDT) plugin** and the **ANSI Escape in Console plugin** in Eclipse.

1. Installation of the AspectJ Development Tools (AJDT) plugin in Eclipse

AspectJ is a Java extension for the development of aspect-oriented applications. There are several plugins to integrate AspectJ with the most popular development environments, facilitating the editing, compilation and debugging of projects that contain aspects, in a simple and friendly way. That is the case of Eclipse and the AspectJ Development Tools (AJDT) integration plug-in.

The first step to develop aspects in Eclipse using AspectJ is to install the plug-in AspectJ Development Tools (AJDT). Next, we show the steps to follow.

Step 1. There are several ways to install AJDT. In this document, in particular, we show how to install it using the *Install new software* option available from the *Help* button, within the Eclipse toolbar (another option would be to download the .zip installation file, and unzip it into the Eclipse's installation directory).

Step 2. Once this option is selected, in the dialog you will have to click on the "Add" button, adding in the *title* "AspectJ" (or any other significant name), and in *Location* the address [http: //download.eclipse.org/tools/ajdt/410/dev/update](http://download.eclipse.org/tools/ajdt/410/dev/update).

Here, we suppose the Eclipse *Photon* distribution (version 4.10). If you are using an Eclipse XY distribution, different from Photon (Eclipse 4.10), in the AJDT installation URL <http://download.eclipse.org/tools/ajdt/XY/dev/update> you will have to indicate as XY, instead of 410, the XY version corresponding to your distribution. For example, at [https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eclipse \(software\)](https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eclipse_(software)) you can see which version corresponds to your distribution. **Note** that AJDT is not available for versions up to 4.10 thus, if your Eclipse distribution version is higher to 4.10, yo can use 410 as XY.

Step 3. Several entries will appear in the central part of the dialog box. You will have to click on the "Select All" button and start the installation process with "Next". You must accept the license terms when the installation process requires it. Finally, Eclipse will ask you to restart the IDE for the changes to be effective.

In order to verify that the plug-in has been installed correctly, you have to go to the *Help* menu and choose the *About* option. A dialog box will appear in which you will have to click on the *Installation Details* button. Subsequently, in the *Plug-ins* tab, you can verify that the AspectJ Development Tools and AspectJ Development Tools - UI plug-ins are installed (among others).

To verify that files with the ***.aj** extension and ***.java** files are associated (at least) to the AspectJ/Java editor, you will have to click on Window → Preferences. Subsequently, in the General→Editors section you will have to choose File associations. Make sure that in File types the files with the extension ***.aj** and ***.java** are associated (at least) with the **AspectJ/Java** and **AspectJ/Java** Editor editors (see the following images):

2. Installation of ANSI Escape in Console

Step 1. Go to *Help* → *Eclipse MarketPlace*

Step 2. Search for "ANSI Escape in Console".

The screenshot shows the Eclipse Marketplace interface. At the top, it says "Eclipse Marketplace" and "Eclipse Marketplace". Below that, it says "Select solutions to install. Press Install Now to proceed with installation. Press the 'more info' link to learn more about a solution." There is a search bar with the text "ANSI Escape in console" and a "Go" button. Below the search bar, there are three search results:

- ANSI Escape in Console**: This Eclipse plugin interprets the ANSI escape sequences to color the console output. It works for output text with escape sequences directly from Java, Groovy,... [more info](#)
by Mihai Nita, Apache 2.0
[ansi color console colour](#)
★ 278 Installs: 45,7K (1.086 last month) **Install**
- m2e-chromatic 1.0.1**: Maven launch participant enabling colored output when the ANSI Escape in Console plugin is installed. It can be disabled in the "Launch Extensions" tab of the... [more info](#)
by Sidespin, EPL
[m2e colored output](#)
★ 11 Installs: 1,14K (39 last month) **Install**
- TM Terminal 4.0 20150430 (Mars M7)**: A fully working command-line Terminal inside Eclipse (renamed from "TCF Terminal"). Just press `Ctrl+Alt+T` to open a local command prompt (Terminal).

At the bottom, there is a "Marketplaces" section with three icons. Below that, there are navigation buttons: **< Back**, **Install Now >**, **Finish**, and **Cancel**.

Step 3. Next, you will have to click on the *Install*.

Step 4. Accept license terms and click on *Finish*.

Step 5. Click on *Restart Now*.

